

CRACK PROPAGATION SUBJECTED TO FATIGUE HYSTERESIS
IN COMPOSITES

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Summary

Microscopic investigations especially relating to the inner material degradation due to fatigue loading in composites are described from the quantitative point of views, with the aid of optical tools such as the dark field illumination and the Koehler illumination. Then these fatigue-degraded composites are subjected to the mode I crack propagation and compared to those of virgin state, showing apparent fatigue degradation effect.

Introduction

Fatigue degradation in composites frequently leading toward fracture has come to be more important as their usage lives become longer, their application wider and their being subject to more severe engineering environmental circumstances. However, it seems to be rather difficult to evaluate these inner fatigue-degradation quantitatively, in spite of much effort.

In the present report, several microscopic approach essentially relating to the inner material degradation due to fatigue in composites are described from the quantitative point of views, with the aid of optical tools such as the dark field illumination and the Koehler illumination. Next, these fatigue-degraded composites are subjected to the mode I crack propagation and then compared to those of virgin state to correlate the fatigue degradation inside the material with the crack propagation velocity.

Experimental Techniques

Specimen

10-ply 8-satin woven glassfiber polyester composites with the glass-fiber content of 45 volume % were used. The specimen dimension is 250 mm x 50 mm x 2.9 mm as shown in Figure 1. The fiber directions are lengthwise and widthwise, orthogonally.

Fatigue Loading

The fatigue loading was given by the hydraulic fatigue testing machine "Servopulser" of Shimadzu make of Japan in a sinusoidal stress wave with the stress ratio $\sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max} = 0$ at 5 Hz, where σ_{max} = the maximum stress and σ_{min} = the minimum stress. The distance between jaws for gripping was 100 mm. Initial notch in a specimen was cut after prescribed fatigue loading.

Figure 1 - Specimen dimension
(unit in mm.)

Velocity Gages (1)

The crack propagation velocity was measured by the velocity gages consisting of conducted wires of du Pont conductive silver coating material, placed perpendicular to the crack propagating direction at prescribed intervals. Upon breaking of conducted wires due to the advance of a running crack, electronic output is generated to be stored in the digital memory, from which the elapsed time between adjacent wire breaking of two silver coating lines can be measured and the average crack velocity between two wires can be calculated from the distance between two wires divided by the elapsed time. In the present case, the prescribed interval is 5 mm. The gage arrangement is shown in Figure 2. These velocity gages were applied after the specimen had been subjected to fatigue loading.

Figure 2 - Velocity gage arrangement. The ladder-like conductive wires of du Pont's silver coating material are broken by crack propagation to produce electronic signals, from which the crack velocity can be measured.

Optical Tools

The inner material degradation due to fatigue was investigated by microscopic photograph taken at several prescribed fatigue cycles. With the aid of proper illumination such as the vertical dark field illumination and the Koehler illumination, good-contrasted photographs could be obtained, from which the inner degradation such as the delamination and the fracture of inner fibers was investigated quantitatively. For detail refer to "Experimental Results and Discussions" described later.

S - N Curve

The applied cyclic stress σ_a versus the number of cycles to failure N_f , so-called the S - N curve, is shown in Figure 3, where σ_a means a stress amplitude.

Figure 3 - Applied stress amplitude vs. number of cycles to failure.

Degradation of Strength and Rigidity

The degradation of both strength and rigidity due to fatigue cycles at $\sigma_a = 10 \text{ Kgf/mm}^2$ is shown in Figure 4 as compared to virgin state, where $n =$ arbitrary fatigue cycle, $E_0 =$ virgin rigidity, $E =$ arbitrary rigidity subject to fatigue, $\sigma_F =$ virgin fracture stress, $\sigma_{FR} =$ arbitrary fracture stress subject to fatigue cycle.

In view of Figure 4, both strength and rigidity decrease with the increase in fatigue cycles, and the rigidity decreasing linearly, while the strength nonlinearly showing less sensitive to fatigue degradation.

Figure 4 - Degradation of strength and rigidity due to fatigue cycles. The stress amplitude is 10 Kgf/mm^2 .

Interfacial Delamination

The interfacial delamination area ratio between fibers and matrix was investigated by using the optical microscope with 400 times magnification. In the present case, the vertical dark field illumination (2) was employed, resulting in good photographic results. In this illumination the parallel illuminating light is projected via an objective lens, being focused on the specimen by the special ring-like condenser lens, and these scattered lights are observed to be photographed.

A typical such photograph for $n/N_f = 0.2$ is shown in Figure 5, in which the interfacial delamination between fibers and matrix is recognized by white-shining lattice-like images due to the scattered light. Actually such photographs were taken for individual 2 mm x 2 mm mesh on both surfaces of a specimen at the middle part of the specimen.

Figure 5 - Delamination between matrix and fibers is shown by white-shining images.

Thus obtained result is shown in Figure 6, in which the interfacial delamination area ratio $(A_A)_d = A_d / A_T$, where A_d = the delamination area within a 2 mm x 2 mm mesh, and A_T = the reference area = 2 mm x 2 mm. These are the average values of these 10 $(A_A)_d$ data, i.e., 5 on one specimen surface and another five on the reverse surface.

In view of Figure 6, the delamination increases up to about $n/N_f = 0.6$, however, then decreases as n/N_f increases.

The stress amplitude was 10 Kgf/mm².

Figure 6 - Interfacial delamination area ratio vs. fatigue cycle.

Fracture of Inner Fibers

The fracture of inner fibers due to fatigue degradation can also be observed by the optical tools. The previously-mentioned vertical dark field illumination was employed again in combination with the Koehler illumination (3). Judging from these two kind photographs, the number of fiber fracture inside the material was calculated within 10 individual 2 mm x 2 mm mesh area for each n/N_f as described previously, and the average number of fiber fracture, $(N)_F$, is shown in Figure 7, in which the average number of fiber fracture linearly increases with the increase in fatigue cycle.

The stress amplitude was 10 Kgf/mm².

Figure 7 - Average number of inner fiber fracture vs. fatigue cycle. The stress amplitude is 10 Kgf/mm^2 .

Crack Propagation Velocity

The dynamic crack propagation velocity profiles are shown in Figures 8 and 9, in which \dot{C} = the crack propagation velocity, C = the arbitrary running crack front position and W = the specimen width = 50 mm. The crack propagation velocity was measured by the velocity gages.

In Figure 8, the crack propagation velocity obtained for virgin state, i.e. $n/N_f = 0$, is shown as a function of non-dimensional crack front position. The single edge initiation crack is cut and the velocity gages are applied on the specimen surface.

In Figure 9, the crack propagation velocity obtained for $n/N_f = 0.9$ is shown also as a function of non-dimensional crack front position. The stress amplitude is 10 Kgf/mm^2 , and the single edge initiation crack and the velocity gages are prepared after the specimen is subjected to the prescribed fatigue cycles.

Now in view of Figures 8 and 9, apart from the crack propagation profiles, apparently the crack propagation velocity subjected to fatigue degradation of $n/N_f = 0.9$ shows the lower value all the way, compared to that of virgin state. This reason would be due possibly to the fact of reduction of rigidity, i.e., the Young's modulus reduction shown in Figure 4, and also due to the decrease in stored strain energy for the fatigue

degraded case, since the observed stress-strain curve is almost linear, the area beneath shows the very strain energy governing the crack propagation, so this area becomes smaller in case of fatigue degradation, as the Young's modulus decreases.

Figure 8 - Crack propagation velocity profile for virgin state ($n/N_f = 0$).

Figure 9 - Crack propagation velocity profile for fatigue degradation case ($n/N_f = 0.9$). The stress amplitude is $10 \text{ Kg}/\text{mm}^2$.

Conclusions

During fatigue degradation in composites, the interfacial delamination area ratio and the average number of fiber fracture of inner layers were investigated quantitatively in relation to the fatigue cycles by using the vertical dark field illumination and the Koehler illumination, in combination with the microscopic photography.

It was recognized the interfacial delamination area ratio increased almost linearly while the average number of fiber fracture inside did linearly, both with the increase in the fatigue cycles.

Further the crack propagation velocity affected by the fatigue cycles was measured by use of velocity gages, and compared to that of virgin state, showing considerable fatigue hysteresis effects.

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References

1. Akira Kobayashi, Nobuo Ohtani and Tadashi Sato, "Phenomenological Aspects of Viscoelastic Crack Propagation," Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 18(1974)p.1625.
2. J.H. Richardson, Optical Microscopy for the Materials Science, p.109; Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1971.
3. M. Born and E. Wolf, Principles of Optics, p.524; Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1965.

